

ENERGY ABSORPTION OF THREE-DIMENSIONAL BRAIDED COMPOSITE TUBES

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to examine the specific energy- absorption capability and failure modes of three-dimensional (3-D) braided composite square tubes. The effects of various braiding fibers and their hybrid on energy-absorption capability were discussed. Axial compressive tests have been carried out on those composite square tubes. Based on the experimental observations, the 3-D carbon/epoxy braided composite square tubes splayed first, then bent until final fracture. On the other hand, the crush test of kevlar/epoxy braided composite square tubes exhibited a stable progressive folding failure. This crush load capacity sequence is believed due to better compressive performance of carbon fibers than Kevlar fibers. As for the specific energy absorption capability, C1C2M3 type was 24% higher than C1K2M3 type.

1. INTRODUCTION

The application of three-dimensional (3-D) fabric composites in high-performance structures has continued to expand in recent years, due to their high specific strength, modulus, impact damage tolerance, fracture toughness and structural integrity. As 3-D textile composites replace more unidirectional tape composites and the role of aircraft crashworthiness and survivability becomes more clearly defined, the need to establish the energy absorption characteristics of 3-D textile composites has increased.

In the last decade several studies have demonstrated the ability of composite material to absorb energy under crushing load. Thornton et al. [1] examined the energy absorption in composite tubes with different fiber materials (graphite, kevlar and glass fibers). Their study showed that the

composite tubes exhibit two basic collapse mechanisms, namely, fracture and folding. For tubes made from, or including kevlar fiber, tended to collapse in an unstable mode by buckling rather than by fracture, which led to low values for specific energy absorption. The fracture collapse mechanism is depending upon the tube geometry. Farley [2] also demonstrated that the Gr./E laminated tubes failed in a brittle mode with negligible post crushing integrity, whereas the K/E laminated tubes failed in an according buckling mode similar to the aluminum tubes. Hamada et al.[3] compared the energy absorption of carbon/epoxy and carbon/PEEK composite tubes . The 0° carbon fiber/PEEK tubes had a higher specific energy absorption than angle ply tubes. This high value is interpreted in terms of the high interlaminar toughness of PEEK matrix composites. Hull [4] described the effect of fiber arrangement on progressive crushing in carbon fiber epoxy unidirectional laminated tubes, woven glass cloth/epoxy tubes, filament-wound angle-ply glass fiber/polyester tubes, and in-plane random chopped glass fiber polyester tubes. Farley and Jones [5] established the crushing modes and their controlling mechanisms of continuous- fiber-reinforced composite tubes. They suggested that the crushing response of composite tubes can be categorized into three basic modes : transverse shearing, lamina bending, and local buckling. The mechanisms that control these different crushing modes are a function of the mechanical properties of the constituent materials and the structure of the specimen.

As seen from above reference, considerable data have been developed on the effects of different composite materials on energy absorption and studied failure modes on unidirectional or woven tubes. However, little is known about the three-dimensional braided composite tubes, especially energy absorption and the crushing characteristics. The purpose of this work was to examine the energy absorbing capacity and crushing failure mode of three-dimensional braided composite square tubes. The 2-step braiding process was applied to fabricate three-dimensional braided square tubes preforms with carbon and kevlar fiber.

2. MATERIALS AND TEST SPECIMENS

Three-dimensional braided square tube preforms with HTA-12K E30 (12000 filaments in a single fiber tow) carbon fibers and Kevlar 49 (7100 denier in a tow) were fabricated by a 2-step braiding process [6,7] . The LY564 epoxy resin and HY2954 hardener (Ciba-Geigy CO) were used to infiltrate the 3-D braided preforms. The definition of each braided preform could be found in Table 1, and the physical properties of the materials showed in Table 2. The schematic geometry of the 3-D braided square tube structure is shown in figure 1. The 3-D braided square composite tube specimens were fabricated by vacuum assisted resin transfer molding process. Square tubes normally 10.16 cm (4.00in) in length having inside width of 2.54 (1.00in) were used as test specimens. Tube specimens 10.16 cm (4.00in) in length were cut from the original cured tube of 35 cm in length. One end of each tube was chamfered, such that crushing could be initiated without catastrophic failure of the tube specimen [8].

The failure modes and energy absorption of the 3-D braided square tube specimens were determined by a static crushing test on a Material Testing System (MTS 810). All tubes were compressed at a rate of 0.021 cm/sec (0.008in/sec), until limited crush.

Table 1. Specification of braided square tube preforms

Item	Braiding yarn	Axial yarn	Pitch	Layer
C1C2M3	12K Corbon/28 Tows	24K Corbon/28 Tows	12mm	3
C1K2M3	12K Corbon/28 Tows	7100 den Kevlar/84 Tows	12mm	3
K1K2M3	7100 den Kevlar/28 Tows	7100 den Kevlar/84 Tows	12mm	3

Table 2 Physical properties for 3-D braided composite tubes

Item	Vf(%)	Vaf(%)	Vbf(%)	Td(g/cm ³)	Md(g/cm ³)	Vc(%)	t(mm)	A(mm ²)
C1C2M3	37.85	31.60	6.25	1.3128	1.2474	4.98	2.43	226.94
C1K2M3	40.37	32.04	8.33	1.2387	1.1987	3.23	3.23	304.70
K1K2M3	39.12	33.25	5.87	1.2106	1.1659	3.69	3.17	392.39

Figure 1. The schematic geometry of the 3-D braided square preform

3. CRUSHING CHARACTERISTICS AND FAILURE MODES

3.1 Carbon/epoxy tubes

The crush failure appearances of 3-D carbon /epoxy braided composite tubes were shown in figure

2. During crushing, the chamfered portion was compressed and then crushed progressively by splaying of the tube wall into internal and external fronds. Because of the combination of strong, rigid corners with weak planar sections in the square tubes, the specimen exhibits the stress concentration phenomenon. Thus, much of the crush resistance and initial cracks occurred in the corner portions. When the cracks were initiated, the propagation of cracks was accelerated owing to the edge effect in the corner, resulting in the bending deformation of the planar portions. Finally, the failure appearances changed to bending or combined fracture-bending failure. The major energy absorption mechanisms could be divided into the splitting of the corner portions, bending of the planar portions, and fracture of the yarns as well as the matrix.

Figure 2. Typical crushing characteristics depicting splaying and bending crushing modes

3.2 Kevlar/epoxy tubes

The kevlar/epoxy braided composite square tubes exhibited a stable progressive folding failure during crush test. This type of failure was similar to that of kevlar/epoxy laminated composite and metallic tubes [9,10] shown as figure 3. The crushing process of kevlar/epoxy braided composite square tubes is a cyclic process of local buckling of axial bundles propagating between braiding bundles in the crushed region. The axial bundles buckle only when the applied load reach a critical value, when the axial fibers deform plastically. In the crushing process of 3-D braided tubes the axial bundle fiber is the predominate load carrying component and the braiding bundle fibers constrain the axial bundle fibers to suppress delamination between axial bundle fibers. The occurrence of buckling could be attributed to the plastic deformation of kevlar fibers. In addition, resin fracture was also observed because the maximum failure strain of matrix was reached in local folding. The major energy absorption mechanism always involved tube buckling. Fracture, when it occurred, tended to be a secondary nature occurring as a consequence of tube buckling, rather than as a precursor to it.

Figure 3. Typical crushing mode of 3-D K/E braided composite tube

3.3 Failure mode on crushing zone

In order to study the crushing failure mode, the crushed specimens were embedded in epoxy resin, and the surfaces of the crushed zone parallel and normal to the tube wall were then polished and inspected under optical microscope. The results are shown in figure 4. It is observed in the Figure 4 that all of compressive shear failure, bending fracture, local buckling of the axial bundles, shear and tensile failure of the braiding bundles, matrix crush, interface debonding and open mode crack propagation take place during the failure process.

Figure 4. Polished section of crush zone of 3-D C/E braided composite tube

4. SPECIFIC ENERGY-ABSORPTION CAPABILITY

Typical load/displacement curves for 3-D braided composite specimens using various braiding yarns are shown in figure 5. The Curve for the 3-D carbon fiber braided composite tube shows two distinct load levels. At the higher loading level the specimen failed by splaying, whereas at the lower loading level it failed by bending. During the experiment, the load built up at initially to a maximum value and then dropped to a lower level in a serrated fashion. The serration was associated with axial splitting and fracture due to lost of constraint force from the braiders. In addition, it can also be cause by fracture of yarns and resin pocket portions resulted from the inherent damage containment unit of the yarn crossing point.

Figure 6 depicted the crush load of composite tubes made with various yarn and hybrid types. Because the carbon fibers can sustain higher compressive forces than the Kevlar fibers, the sequence in terms of the maximum crush load for those various composites is C1C2M3, C1K2M3 and K1K2M3. Therefore, the type of the axial yarns is the dominate factor in determining the maximum crush load. As for the specific energy absorption, C1C2M3 is higher than C1C2M3, as shown in figure 7. This is because C1K2M3 has shorter crush distance. On the other hand, the specific energy absorption of C1K2M3 is 24% higher than that of K1K2M3. This result indicates that the carbon fibers can absorb more energy than Kevlar fibers in crush test.

Figure 5. Load-displacement curves of 3-D braided composite tubes made with various yarn and hybrid types

Figure 6 The crush load of 3-D braided composite tubes made with various yarn and hybrid types

Figure 7 The energy absorption of 3-D braided composite tubes made with various yarn and hybrid types

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Based on the experimental observations, the 3-D carbon/epoxy braided composite square tubes splayed first, then bent until final fracture. On the other hand, the crush test of kevlar/epoxy braided composite square tubes exhibited a stable progressive folding failure. The failure modes of the crush tests of those composite tubes included compressive shear failure, bending fracture, local buckling of the axials, shear and tensile failure of the braiders, matrix crush, interface debonding and open mode crack propagation. As for the specific energy absorption capability, C1K2M3 type was 24% higher than K1K2M3 type. This higher specific energy absorption capability revealed that the carbon fibers could absorb more energy in crush tests.

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